

Intel and its relation with COVID 19

Artur Victoria

A friend I most consider for its professional career done with the highest competence and with an exemplary dedication, with the highest rank in the Armed Forces, told me, regarding COVID 19 that "theoretically is a topic security, but not a military issue. Hence my appeal to Intel, these missions is to identify threats to national interests."

I was reflecting on these words and decided, in addition to many Papers already written on matters of this theme, to make a schematic outline to justify such a thought with which I agree.

Forewords

March 25th 2020 - In view of the situation of "absolute exception", with "very significant implications for the area of civil protection", the National Emergency Plan for Civil Protection (PNEPC) was activated in Portugal. As the Secretary of State for Internal Administration explained when announcing it, this Tuesday, this is "a fundamental operational management tool for the system" of civil protection and will allow "progress in what are the mechanisms of institutional coordination and management operational in a more concerted way than would have been possible before".

In the current situation, caused by the pandemic and with a total of around 50 municipal emergency and civil protection plans active in the country and nine district plans, "it made perfect sense to assess the pertinence of activating the national plan so that there is a consistency in what are the management instruments within the scope of civil protection ", explained Patrícia Gaspar:" In practice, it is so that there is a correspondence at the national level of all the work that is already being done at the local and district level".

According to the defined framework, the activation of the PNEPC is applicable "to the cases of imminence or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe", whose consequences "expected or verified" are serious and of a size that may require the activation of public and / or private means additional.

Scenarios such as earthquakes, floods and fires of serious proportions are some of the criteria to justify the activation of the Plan, which also includes as a criterion "significant and direct effects on the population causing more than 1000 displaced, injured or killed" or "other circumstances, according with the imminence or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe".

A -

I

General introduction

Mission is the guiding point of the cycle, it is the factor of the operational environment that dominates Intelligence Operations. Meeting the Intelligence needs that the mission imposes is the fundamental purpose of Intelligence Operations.

There are certain basic principles that apply to Intelligence, whatever the requirements, available means or environments in which Intelligence Operations take place.

The application of these principles are largely a matter of discretion on the part of the Intelligence since sometimes the relative importance of one and the other seems to make them enter into conflict, so it is necessary to take into account their true value and be able to complement them. . These are:

a) **Usefulness:** Intelligence must be adequate for its use, it must increase knowledge and understanding of the particular problem under consideration, to serve as the basis for the decision.

A full understanding of the nature of the problem or the mission it is essential for the production of useful Intelligence; this implies early knowledge of the nature of Intelligence required so that it is not the simple aspect of increasing knowledge, which could be interesting but not useful.

b) **Opportunity:** Intelligence must be timely, its value is in reaching the user in time for its use so that it can serve as a basis for appropriate action. Sometimes the opportunity may involve some sacrifice regarding the integrity and accuracy of the knowledge obtained; it can present itself in a situation that needs an immediate decision that cannot be postponed.

An understanding of the proper use of the problem or mission is a guide to the degree of accuracy and completeness so as not to miss the job opportunity.

c) **Flexibility:** Procedures that cannot be changed to meet the requirements of a given situation generally lead to failure. Although regulatory procedures generally make Intelligence more effective, they are not followed blindly. Procedures are flexible to meet unexpected requirements. Intelligence based on reason and judgment and not on fixed procedures is more adapted to tactical situations.

d) **Security:**

1- The nature of intelligence requires constant security measures to deny unauthorized personnel information about the operations of the Intelligence bodies, information sources and the Intelligence product.

Deception measures are taken to hide cash and intent. Knowledge of the extent to which these measures have been successful is of great value.

2- While the effects of engagement from full studies and Intelligence Appraisals are obvious, the cumulative effects of engagement are also dangerous. All the people involved to obtain and use pieces of information to develop a complete presentation of Intelligence.

3- A clear distinction is made between security and secrecy. Intelligence only has value if it reaches the authorized user. Security measures should not hinder the disclosure of information to those who require it. Organs must freely and completely exchange information and intelligence to allow the best possible production.

e) Imagination

1- Intelligence Operations require imagination and insight. Norms and procedures that limit the imagination or initiative of subordinate organs are avoided. Intelligence personnel use ingenuity so that all available information can be developed and exploited and the resulting Intelligence can be provided to the user in an appropriate way.

2- The self-evident is never accepted without taking extreme caution.

3- Intelligence is based on the assumption that the situation always changes and does not remain fixed. During periods of relative inactivity, Intelligence is designed to discover any signs of change in the situation of a true or potential danger

In these moments, the meaning of Intelligence, and even the lack thereof, assumes immediate importance. The doubt as to the probability of adoption of the danger possibilities is resolved in favour of positive failure of the mission. Blind acceptance of the continuity of a current situation can be fatal.

II

Planning

Intelligence planning requires anticipation of information requirements to meet the security and surveillance needs of the organization. Intelligence planning indicates changing conditions by developing and exploiting good sources of information, improving methods, and increasing the effectiveness of information dissemination.

It results in the search for information on topics of current interest and value in the future. If Improper Intelligence is developed on any topic of current interest, corrective action is taken without delay. Intelligence personnel take the initiative in the search for information that seems to be useful, in addition to the information specifically requested by the mission and this requires complete Planning.

III Intelligence cycle

The cycle for the production of Intelligence comprises four phases:

- 1- The orientation of the search effort.
- 2- The search for information.
- 3- The processing of the information obtained to produce Intelligence.
- 4- The use of the resulting Intelligence.

These four phases are simultaneous. At the same time that new information is being sought, others already obtained are in the process of transformation and, simultaneously, the intelligence produced is being used. All these operations must be constantly oriented.

These four operations constitute the common denominator of the "intelligence cycle". Each of them is indispensable, since if one of them fails, the entire cycle will fail. Signs

III Signs

The indications are evidence or evidences of the situation or activities (positive or negative) and of the terrain or meteorological conditions that allow us to discover the adoption and elimination of a certain possibility. The lack of positive indications regarding an action can strengthen those that are oriented to another action.

1 - Application

The indications as to its application to intelligence may progressively reveal the most imminent possibility of the danger. The expression: "the events to be produced are anticipated by their shadows" gives an idea of the relationship between the indications and the adequate responses it is convenient to look for those events that cast shadow to determine what will happen next.

2 - Determination

The analysis allows determining the specific elements of information that will serve as a guide to find the answers. These specific elements of information are determined in light of:

1- Complete knowledge of the dangers

2- Knowledge of the personality of the people operating and their superiors

IV The search resources

The search resources are directed towards specific Intelligence objectives according to the priority with which they are needed.

The priorities reflect the urgency of a particular information but there is no formula with which such priorities can be automatically determined, since this would be left to the discretion and experience of the Unit Intelligence Officer and thus it can be seen that an Intelligence matter who has priority in one situation or in a Unit, may not have it in another given situation or in any other Unit.

Intelligence needs are divided into two categories: the Essential Information Elements (EIE) and the Other Intelligence Requirements (OIR).

After the EIEs have been expressed, orders and requests for information are issued in a defined and precise manner to the search agencies. To avoid omissions, the Intelligence Officer prepares the Search Plan, which consists, first, of an analysis of the EIE and then establishes the search scheme based on that analysis. It is normally done on a special format sheet that should be used by all the staff of the Intelligence Section and that constitutes only a worksheet, for which reason it should not be disseminated.

The Intelligence Officer can, during the combat, reduce his Search Plan to a simple mental analysis, then deciding the search bodies that will obtain the information. You can also prepare fragmentary notes that will allow you to develop an abbreviated Search Plan. However, according to time and situation, it is preferable to develop a detailed plan. Regardless, the Intelligence Officer must follow an orderly process to consider:

The EIE.

b. The indications.

c. Orders and requests.

d. Search bodies.

e) The time and place of sending the information.

V Intelligence Plan

The Intelligence Plan contains a summary of the Intelligence situation, the essential information elements and the Intelligence requirements and will include other aspects related to the activity of Intelligence. In this way, it facilitates the issuance of orders in

a timely manner and coordinates the diffusion of orders and the available intelligence means.

1- The Intelligence Plan does not constitute a static document; it will undergo continuous modifications aimed at perfecting and updating it.

2- The form of the Intelligence Plan is the same as the "Intelligence Annex". The explanation of each paragraph will be made in the Intelligence Planning Chapter.

3- The Intelligence Plan is normally prepared at the General Secretary level, similar or higher.

B –

1 - Sources

Information sources are considered to be any person, object or act from which information is obtained about the danger, and the situation conditions. The sources of information are multiple and varied. At the beginning of operations, the Intelligence Officer will always have information that, converted into Intelligence, will allow him to prepare an initial Assessment.

As operations progress, the Intelligence Officer and its search agencies discover and develop new sources of information. Considerable effort and ingenuity are required to get the most out of available information sources.

C –

1 – Information processing

Information processing is the operation within the Intelligence Cycle through which the information received is converted into Intelligence; this process comprises the following three steps:

a- Registry.

b- Evaluation.

c- Interpretation.

The processing of information is done according to its importance; the information that refers to the area of influence is generally processed with a higher priority than that related to the area of interest.

2. Processing procedures

1- The information is processed at the same time it is obtained without waiting for any additional information. The intelligence obtained by processing incomplete information may in some cases be essential. For example, there is always a gap between the reconstruction of a target and the time when the information is available. It may happen that the complete information of a target is fully available when the target has already begun to dissipate, which will go against waiting for more information instead of using what comes even when it is incomplete.

However, to the extent of the available time, a search for additional information is ordered to complete, refute or confirm the Intelligence obtained based on incomplete information.

2- The order of succession of operations in processing depends on the nature and urgency of the information, generally registration is the first step to follow. However, it can occur simultaneously with the evaluation and interpretation or in some cases this registration is made after the other operations, including after the dissemination.

3- The information requested by the adjacent Superior Units and which is for immediate use is transmitted when obtained. Information that is not of current interest but is valuable for the future is fully processed. Information that is not relevant is not processed.

4- The processing has as a general rule, that information is not transmitted to the subordinate without the corresponding process, that is, that intelligence must be transmitted from the upper echelon to the subordinate; however, in some cases the Upper Rung may transmit unprocessed information. The subordinate Step may also be requested to process the information before it is transmitted to the upper Step.

3- Processing and appreciation of intelligence

Information processing is an important aspect of Intelligence Operations, as this gathering of Intelligence is used to constantly update Intelligence Appreciation.

1- As the information is processed, new Intelligence is obtained and this affects the existing Appreciation.

2- The conclusions can be altered or confirmed; new possibilities can be determined and a new relative probability of adoption established.

D -

1- Evaluation

Evaluation is a critical appraisal that is used as a basis for subsequent interpretation. In reality, it is a prior analysis that determines the path that the information that is the

object of the processing will follow; In this phase the relevance of the information, the reliability of the source and the organ, and the accuracy of the information are determined.

1- The evaluation actually has the following functions:

- a. Previous analysis of the information.
- b. Guarantee the validity of the source and the body.
- c. Determine the accuracy of the information content.

2- Relevance

Relevance determines the importance of the information, specifically in the following:

- 1- If it is information of immediate need.
- 2- If it is information of possible current value or of future value.

Once this aspect has been determined, the information can be immediately disseminated and will continue in the evaluation process; this process in many occasions is almost simultaneous.

3 - Reliability

1- The degree of confidence is an evaluation made by the Intelligence Officer to determine the credibility given by the origin of that information, before proceeding to the evaluation of the information as such.

2- The main basis for determining the degree of confidence of a source and an organ is previous experience. An aspect normally to consider is the condition under which the information was obtained.

4- Accuracy

1- Accuracy refers to the veracity of the information; it is based on giving answers to the following questions:

- a- Is the reported fact possible?
- b- Is the report consistent in itself?
- c- Is the report confirmed or corroborated by other information that comes from different sources or bodies?
- d- In what aspect do you agree or disagree with other information already received regarding the same matter, particularly with the Intelligence that you already have?

e- If the information disagrees with other information, which one is more likely to be true?

2- The most reliable method of judging accuracy is by comparing it to other information. The Intelligence Officer, to the extent possible, obtains the same information through different bodies or from numerous sources.

3- It may happen that marked differences occur in the appreciation of the accuracy of the information. However, this is a normal aspect since the Upper Echelon has a greater number of organs and can exploit a greater number of sources.

5- Valuation of the source, the body and the information

1- The evaluation of each item of information is indicated by a system of letters and figures. The evaluation classifications are made in the Lesser Command, since the closest body is the best judge of the source's confidence, normally the Superior Command accepts that evaluation or confidence classification, but qualifies the confidence of the reporting Command.

2- The letters used for the evaluation of the source and the organ is as follows:

A Completely reliable.

B Generally reliable.

C Reliable but not at all times.

D Generally unreliable.

E Not trustworthy.

F Trust cannot be judged.

Normally the font is evaluated with the letter B onwards, since A is an evaluation assigned to extraordinary circumstances. Also, an F rating is made when there is no basis for appreciating the trust of the source.

3- Accuracy assessment

Like trust in the source and the body, the information is evaluated for its accuracy, using figures as follows:

1.- Confirmed by other sources or bodies.

2.- Probably true.

3.- Possibly true.

4.- Its veracity is doubtful.

5.- Unlikely (probably uncertain).

6.- The veracity cannot be judged.

4- With the evaluation of the source and the organ and the evaluation of the accuracy, the evaluation of an information is then made with the combination of letter and number; however, it must be taken into account that the assignment of letters and numbers must be done independently of each one; thus, for example, there may be information A1 or A5 and also E1 or E5; the evaluation is a matter of discretion of the Intelligence Officer and is highly dependent on experience.

E-

Presentation

The interpretation determines the importance of the information with respect to what is already known and leads to conclusions regarding the probable meaning of the information already evaluated. Interpretation is the result of critical judgment comprising:

1- Analysis.

2- Integration.

3- Conclusion.

1- Analysis is the investigation and classification of information to isolate those significant elements with respect to the mission and operations of the Command concerned; it requires good judgment and a thorough knowledge of the principles of operations.

2- The analysis encompasses a more detailed investigation; increases in difficulties as the volume of information increases.

2- Integration

1- It is the combination of the isolated elements in the analysis with other known information to form a logical concept, establishing hypotheses of the danger activities or of the influence of the characteristics of the Operations Area on the mission of the Command. This development of hypotheses requires knowledge and judgment, bearing in mind that the enemy's intentions must not be assumed or put in his place but in a logical location, of the facts presented, in time and space.

2- The hypotheses are analyzed and tested. This analysis includes determining the clues that should exist for it to be valid. The verification is made by verifying the existence or not of these signs within the time and means available. Depending on the

problem, integration can be a short (mental) process or a long process, including additional search for information.

- Conclusion.

Hypotheses developed and tested, considered valid in the integration process, the conclusion is reached; which normally answers the question, what meaning does this information have in relation to the current Intelligence situation?

Pre-Conclusion

The ultimate purpose of intelligence it is the dissemination.

The adequate diffusion of Intelligence can be judged from the point of view of its priority, taking into account the following criteria.

1- Information

Such as intelligence must be placed in a timely manner in the hands of the person who will primarily use it, in order to allow its evaluation and interpretation, the formulation of plans and the initiation of action under existing conditions, before the picture changes.

2- Intelligence.

If the information is disseminated without processing, it can be clearly indicated that said information has not been evaluated. If security permits, the source of the information will be identified.

1- Only essential Intelligence of interest to the unit under consideration will be disseminated.

2- The importance and priority of disseminated intelligence will be carefully considered. The means of communication chosen for broadcasting must be such that they produce the least intelligence in the operation of the communications system.

Conclusion

Effectively what has been noticed in this pandemic situation of the COVID19 virus has:

1 - Speculative information and misinformation;

2 - The inexistence of an information service dedicated to epidemics and catastrophes with truly professional characteristics that allow the various operational commands and decision makers to perceive the dangerous situation, its permanent evolution. This intelligence information service must have the characteristics of this mission like:

- Detection of the epidemic, catastrophe or fire-starting forest fires;
- Operational intelligence staff in the affected or potentially affected areas;
- Professional intelligence work through the methods succinctly proposed for its dissemination to the operational posts, operational commands and or policy makers.

I therefore agree with my esteemed General that this COVID 19 is a matter of national security and as such it should be dealt with in the future, in cooperation with international counterparts.

References:

Plano Nacional de Emergência de Proteção Civil

Best, Richard A., Jr. and Elizabeth B. Bazan. "Intelligence Spending: Public Disclosure Issues." IN Haas, Philipp R. *Intelligence Oversight and Disclosure Issues*. Hauppauge, NY: Nova Science Publishers, 2010. p.

Born, Hans and Ian Leigh, *Handbook on Making Intelligence Accountable: Legal Standards and Best Practice for Oversight of Intelligence Agencies*. Oslo, Norway: Parliament of Norway, 2005. 143p. [available online in various languages]

Borrow, Davis B. "Security Futures: Intelligence and Intelligence." p. 55-71, IN *Planning U.S. Security: Defense Policy in the Eighties, A Study*, Philip S. Kronenberg (ed). Washington, DC: National Defense University Press, 1981. 214p

Bruce, James B. "The Impact on Foreign Denial and Deception of Increased Availability of Public Information About U.S. intelligence." IN Godson, Roy and James J. Wirtz (Eds.). *Strategic Denial and Deception: The Twenty-First Challenge*. p. 229-240. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction Publishers, 2002. 256p.

Chapman, Bert. *Researching National Security and Intelligence Policy*. Washington, DC: CQ Press, 2004. 452p.

Charters, David A. et al (eds.). *Intelligence Analysis and Assessment*. Portland, OR: Frank Cass, 1996. 228p. DKL UB 250 .I57 1996 GENERAL

Cimbala, Stephen J. (ed.) *Intelligence and Intelligence Policy in a Democratic Society*. Dobbs Ferry, NY: Transactional Publishers, 1987. 262p.

Cummings, Alfred. *Congress as a Consumer of Intelligence Information*. R40136. Washington, DC: Library of Congress, Congressional Research Service, [various]. <http://openocrs.com/document/R40136/>

DCAF Intelligence Working Group, *Intelligence Practice and Democratic Oversight – a Practitioner’s View*. DCAF, Occasional paper no. 3. August 2003. 79p.

Dunn, William L. "Intelligence and Decisionmaking." IN Alfred C. Maurer, et al. (eds.) *Intelligence Policy and Process*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, 1985, p. 220-234.

George, Roger Z. and James B. Bruce. (eds) *Analyzing Intelligence: Origins, Obstacles, and Innovations*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University, 2008. 340p. DKL JK 468 .I6 A843 2008 GENERAL

George, Roger Z. and Robert D. Kline. *Intelligence and the National Security Strategist: Enduring Issues and Challenges*. Washington, DC: National Defense University, 2004. 564p.

Hedley, John Hollister. *Checklist for the Future of Intelligence*. Washington, DC: Institute for the Study of Diplomacy, Edmund A. Walsh School of Foreign Service, Georgetown University, 1995. 33p.

McCarthy, Shaun P. *The Function of Intelligence in Crisis Management*. Brookfield, VT: Ashgate, 1998. 311p.

McDonald McDowell, Don. *Strategic Intelligence: A Handbook for Practitioners, Managers and Users*. Lanham, MD: Scarecrow, 2009. 272p.

Terchek, Ronald J. "Strategic Intelligence and the Formulation of Public Policy." p. 70-93 IN *Interaction, Foreign Policy and Public Policy*, Frank B. Feigert (ed) Washington, DC: American Enterprise Institute for Public Policy Research, 1983. 235p.